

1 **Stem rust of cereals undergo sexual reproduction in barberry species present in Europe**

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25 diversity

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30 Abstract

31 The increased emergence of cereal stem rust, caused by *Puccinia graminis*, and the prevalence of
32 the alternate (sexual) host, *Berberis* species, in cereal growing areas in Europe have recently
33 regained the attention due to the potential detrimental effect that the sexual cycle may pose to cereal
34 supply. The main objective of the present study was to investigate the potential role of *Berberis*
35 species in the epidemiology of cereal stem rust fungi. Systematic surveys across eleven European
36 countries were carried out collecting aecial infections from barberry species present in Europe.
37 Phylogenetic analysis using the EF1- α indicated the presence of multiple special forms (aka *formae*
38 *speciales*) of *P. graminis* infecting wheat, rye, oat and multiple other related grasses. Host
39 specificity studies using sexually-derived populations from Spain, UK and Switzerland further
40 confirmed the presence of multiple *formae speciales* of *P. graminis* infecting major cereal crops.
41 Subsequent population genetic analysis of these sexual populations revealed high

42 This new fundamental knowledge on the role of the alternate host in cereal rust epidemiology will
43 be crucial as sexual reproduction potentially increase genetic variability in cereal rust populations
44 and thereby pose a threat to cereal production in Europe and beyond.

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48 1. Introduction

49 Stem rust diseases, caused by the basidiomycete *Puccinia graminis sensu lato*, are a major threat
50 to cereal production globally (Singh et al., 2016;Saunders et al., 2019). Stem rust of cereals present
51 unique features in their life cycles including asexual reproduction on the primary cereal host and
52 sexual reproduction on a phylogenetically unrelated alternate host (Stubbs, 1985;Jin et al., 2010).
53 Sexual reproduction provides advantages regarding the generation of novel genetic and virulence
54 combinations that may endanger the durability of cereal rust resistance and a stable cereal supply
55 (Burdon and Roelfs, 1985;Billiard et al., 2012;Zhao et al., 2016). Additionally, the presence of the
56 alternate host increases the level of initial fungal inoculum and advances the onset of the disease
57 (Roelfs, 1982;Peterson et al., 2005). To date, approximately 100 species belonging to the
58 *Berberidaceae* family, specifically to the *Berberis* and *Mahonia* genera, and interspecific hybrids,
59 have been confirmed susceptible to *P. graminis* (Ahrendt, 1961;Roelfs, 1985;Zhao et al., 2016).
60 This includes *Berberis vulgaris* (aka European or common barberry) that is the most widely
61 distributed barberry specie in Europe. The incidence of common barberry in Europe has
62 significantly increased due to the repeal of eradication campaigns and legislation banning the
63 planting of barberry plants near cereal crops and its re-introduction promoted by natural
64 conservationists (Berlin et al., 2013b;Saunders et al., 2019). Besides common barberry, indigenous
65 barberry species such as *B. vulgaris* subsp. *seroi* and *B. vulgaris* subsp. *australis* in Spain (López
66 González, 1986) and *B. aetnensis* in Italy (Ahrendt, 1961), and interspecific hybrids, are present in
67 Europe and potentially play a role in the epidemiology of cereal rust fungi (Villegas et al., 2022).

68 The implementation of barberry eradication programs during the 20th century resulted in a
69 reduction in the initial inoculum and the genetic variability generated in the alternate host, and

70 ultimately in the stabilization of *P. graminis* races (Stakman, 1923;Hermansen, 1968;Roelfs,
71 1982). Consequently, no significant outbreaks of cereal stem rust have occurred in the last decades
72 and thus the pathogen considered as a vanquished foe due to the effect of barberry eradication in
73 addition to the deployment of cereal varieties carrying durable resistance genes (Stakman,
74 1923;Peterson et al., 2005;Peterson, 2018). Unfortunately, the emergence and posterior evolution
75 and spread of a highly virulent race in East Africa in 1998, commonly known as Ug99, left 90% of
76 the wheat germplasm grown globally susceptible to stem rust (Pretorius et al., 2000;Singh et al.,
77 2011). Recently, stem rust has resurged in Western Europe causing multiple outbreaks on
78 particularly bread and durum wheat and it is now considered as a re-emerged cereal foe (Saunders
79 et al., 2019), e.g., Italy (Bhattacharya, 2017), Sweden (Berlin, 2017) and Germany (Olivera Firpo
80 et al., 2017). Additionally, the role of the alternate host on cereal stem rust variability has regained
81 attention due to the detection of pathogen races carrying unusual virulence combinations associated
82 with the presence of the alternate host in Europe and beyond (Berlin et al., 2013b;Berlin et al.,
83 2014;Olivera Firpo et al., 2017;Olivera et al., 2019).

84 *Puccinia graminis* comprises special forms (aka *formae speciales*, ff. spp.) adapted to certain cereal
85 hosts, such as *P. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* infecting wheat (*Pgt*), *P. graminis* f.sp. *secalis* infecting rye
86 (*Pgs*) and *P. graminis* f.sp. *avenae* infecting oat (*Pga*) (Eriksson and Henning, 1894;Anikster,
87 1984). Barberry species are alternate hosts for these ff. spp. in addition to several other *Puccinia*
88 species, e.g., *P. striiformis*, *P. brachypodii* and *P. arrhenatheri* (Cummins and Greene, 1966;Naef
89 et al., 2002;Jin et al., 2010). However, the genetic subdivision of *Puccinia* species is still poorly
90 understood (Berlin et al., 2013a). Since the aecial structures formed on barberry species have a
91 similar morphology, molecular-based methods such as DNA fingerprinting in addition to *in vivo*
92 experiments using aecial samples via inoculation on cereal and grass hosts are needed to identify
93 the cereal rust species that undergo sexual reproduction (Berlin et al., 2017;Lewis et al., 2018).
94 Additionally, by applying molecular approaches such as neutral molecular markers on sexually-
95 derived cereal rust samples, the genetic variability generated among fungal samples and
96 populations can be determined (Zambino et al., 2000;Rodriguez-Algaba et al., 2017). DNA
97 sequencing using both the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region and the translation elongation
98 factor 1- α (EF1- α) gene have previously been used to identify ff. spp. of *P. graminis* formed in the
99 cereal/grass host (Zambino and Szabo, 1993;Abbasi et al., 2005). However, less attention has been
100 put to characterize the aecial structures formed on barberry species and infer in the cereal rust
101 species that may undergo sexual reproduction. To date, only a few of studies have reported on the
102 *Puccinia* species and/or genera infecting barberry species in local areas in Europe (Berlin et al.,
103 2013a;Lewis et al., 2018;Villegas et al., 2022). Thus, detailed DNA-based and cereal host
104 specificity studies investigating the cereal rust species infecting barberry species and major cereal
105 crops across Europe are still lacking.

106 The detrimental role that the alternate host may pose to cereal supply has recently drawn the
107 attention due to the increased emergence of stem rust and the prevalence of the alternate host in
108 cereal growing areas in Europe. This has been reflected in a new European initiative launched in
109 2018 aiming to develop an early-warning system for cereal rust diseases (Hovmøller, 2018). The
110 main objective of the present study was to investigate the potential role of *Berberis* species in the
111 epidemiology of cereal rust fungi by identifying the rust genera and/or species that infect the
112 alternate host, barberry species, across Europe. Additionally, we evaluated which rust species may
113 undergo sexual reproduction and subsequently infect major cereal crops and investigated the
114 genetic diversity generated on the cereal host. This new fundamental knowledge on the role of the

115 alternate host in cereal rust epidemiology will be crucial as sexual reproduction potentially increase
 116 genetic variability in cereal rust populations and thereby pose a threat to cereal production in
 117 Europe and beyond.

118 **2. Materials and methods**

119 **2.1 Sample and data collection**

120 From 2018 to 2020, barberry leaves bearing aecia of five barberry species, i.e., *B. vulgaris*, *B.*
 121 *aetnensis*, *B. vulgaris* subsp. *seroi*, *B. vulgaris* subsp. *australis* and *B. x ottawensis* (an interspecific
 122 hybrid of *B. vulgaris* and *B. thunbergii*) were collected in 11 European countries (Fig. 1). A total
 123 of 166 barberry samples, containing multiple rust infected leaves, were sampled from multiple
 124 surveyed sites with an elevation ranging from 1 to 2000 meters above sea level (masl) and a
 125 distance to cereals and grass fields of approximately 0 to 20000 m (Supplementary Table 1).
 126 Identification of barberry species was verified based on particular morphological characteristics,
 127 e.g., color of one year old stems, color of matured fruits, and type and morphology of racemes and
 128 leaves, according to Ahrendt (1961) and (López González, 1986). The infected leaves contained
 129 multiple aecial clusters varying in the number of aecial cups. Leaves were placed in glycine or
 130 paper bags to promote rapid drying and to avoid leaf curling. Infected barberry leaves were selected
 131 based on the non-degraded appearance of aecia clusters and were used to investigate host
 132 specificities on cereal crops and for DNA sequencing. Poor and degraded aecia were only used for
 133 DNA sequencing.

134
 135 **Figure 1.** Infected barberry leaves were collected from five barberry species at multiple surveyed sites in
 136 11 European countries.

137 **2.2 DNA sequencing and phylogenetic analysis of aecial clusters**

138 Prior PCR amplification, DNA was extracted from dried single aecial clusters using...

139 Aecial sequences were assembled and aligned using the QIAGEN CLC Genomics Workbench v.
 140 20.0.4 (<https://digitalinsights.qiagen.com>) and apparent misalignments manually examined. After
 141 trimming, all sequences were aligned and a consensus sequence generated for each sample. The
 142 Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLASTN) were used to find similarities between sequences
 143 in GenBank, NCBI (Altschul et al., 1997). Rust specie identity of samples was determined by the
 144 maximum identity observed compared to sequences available in GenBank. A maximum-likelihood
 145 phylogenetic tree was generated using the Neighbor Joining construction method with bootstrap
 146 values generated from 1000 replicates. The General Time Reversible nucleotide substitution model
 147 was used according to the model testing tool implemented in the QIAGEN CLC Genomics
 148 Workbench, which allow to identify the most appropriate substitution model to be used for
 149 maximum likelihood phylogeny tree construction (Yang, 1994). The resulting phylogenetic tree
 150 was visualized using iTOL v. 6.5.2 (Letunic and Bork, 2021). Five reference EF1- α sequences
 151 obtained from NCBI in addition to 14 internal references from multiple *Puccinia* species infecting
 152 various cereal and grass hosts were included in the phylogenetic analysis as multiple fungal species
 153 have been reported to infect the alternate host, barberry species (Supplementary Table 2) (e.g.
 154 Berlin et al., 2013a;Zhao et al., 2016).

155

156 **2.3 Aecial host specificities**

157 Host specificities of *P. graminis* ff. spp. were investigated by pooled aecia inoculations on varieties
 158 of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* var. Morocco and Line E), rye (*Secale cereale* var. Prolific), barley
 159 (*Hordeum vulgare* var. Hiproly), and oat (*Avena sativa* var. Marvellous) using aeciospores from
 160 barberry leaves collected in Spain and UK, and using var. Line E, Cartago and Prolific from
 161 barberry leaves collected in Switzerland. These varieties are considered as ‘universal’ susceptible
 162 varieties of *P. graminis* ff. spp. including *Pgt* (var. Morocco, Line E, and Hiproly), *Pgs* (var. Line
 163 E, Hiproly, and Prolific), and *Pga* (var. Marvelous) (Villegas et al., 2022). Additionally, wheat
 164 varieties Cartago and Morocco were also included as these are considered as ‘universal’ susceptible
 165 varieties for the yellow/stripe wheat rust fungus, *P. striiformis* f.sp. *tritici* (Milus et al.,
 166 2015;Hovmøller et al., 2017). Twenty seeds of each variety were grown in square plastic pots and
 167 when the seedlings were approximately 2-4 cm, 3 ml of maleic hydrazine solution (Antergon®,
 168 MH 180, Crompton Registrations Ltd., Birmingham, England) was added to slow plant growth and
 169 enhance spore production. Two pots of each cereal variety were randomized and placed bellow
 170 barberry leaves bearing aecia, which were fixed to a plastic stand, misted with water and incubated
 171 at 15°C for 24h in darkness, 100% relative humidity (RH). Subsequently, seedlings were
 172 transferred to spore-proof greenhouse cabins and kept at 18°C day/14°C night with a photoperiod
 173 of 16 h of natural light and supplementary artificial light (200 $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$), RH 80%. Uredinia
 174 resembling the stem rust fungus were observed from 10 days after aeciospore exposure on all cereal
 175 varieties. When clearly separated pustules developed, leaf segments of approximately 1-3 cm were
 176 detached and rinsed with water to remove possible spores from additional lesions. Leaf segments
 177 bearing uredinia were then dried for 2 days in a desiccator at room temperature and stored until
 178 further use.

179 **2.4 DNA extraction and molecular genotyping of uredinial isolates**

180 Genomic DNA was extracted from dried leaf segments harboring single lesions of *P. graminis*
 181 sampled from the cereal varieties used in the aecial host specificity test as described above.

182 **2.5 Population genetic analyses of uredinial isolates**

183 The “*poppr*” package version 2.9.3 implemented in the R environment was used for genetic
 184 analyses of sexually derived uredinial isolates from three populations, i.e., Spain, England and
 185 Switzerland, and from three cereal hosts, i.e., wheat, barley, and rye (Kamvar et al., 2014; Kamvar
 186 et al., 2015). Population genetic analyses included number of observed MLGs showing genotypic
 187 richness, G/N number of MLGs divided by number of samples, Simpson’s index (λ)
 188 measuring genetic diversity (Simpson, 1949), evenness distribution of genotype abundance (E_5)
 189 (Grünwald et al., 2003), and Nei’s unbiased gene diversity (H_{exp}) (Nei, 1978). Analyses of
 190 molecular variance (AMOVA) and subsequent significant tests were performed on clone corrected
 191 data to evaluate molecular differences among populations and host of origin (Excoffier et al.,
 192 1992). The fixation index (F_{st}) measuring pairwise divergence between populations, the number of
 193 effective migrants ($N_m = [(1/F_{st})-1]/4$) and Nei’s genetic distance were assessed using GenAlEx
 194 6.503 with 9999 permutations and bootstraps (Wright, 1965; Nei, 1972; Peakall and Smouse,
 195 2006; Peakall and Smouse, 2012). Pearson’s correlation coefficients (ρ) were calculated to measure
 196 the linear correlation between F_{st} , N_m and Nei’s genetic distance values.

197 The population structure of related sexually derived uredinial isolates was analysed by
 198 Discriminant Analysis of Principal Components (DAPCs) using the “*adegenet*” package version
 199 2.1.5 implemented in the R environment (Jombart, 2008; Jombart et al., 2010). The DAPC, which
 200 transforms the MLG genetic data using PCA and subsequently performs a discriminant analysis
 201 (DA) on the PCs retained, is a multivariate non-parametric method without any predetermined
 202 population genetic model with respects to Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium or linkage disequilibrium
 203 (Jombart et al., 2010). The *find.clusters* function, without any predetermined information regarding
 204 the expected number of genetic groups, was used to identify the optimal number of clusters (K).
 205 This is normally associated with the lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) K value, which
 206 is frequently indicated by an elbow in the BIC curve (Jombart et al., 2010). As the number of PCs
 207 retained in the DAPC analysis has a strong impact in the final clustering, a cross-validation function
 208 (*xvalDapc*) with 1000 replicates was implemented to find the optimal number of PCs to be retained,
 209 which was associated with the lowest root mean square error. Subsequently, a scatterplot with the
 210 first and second linear discriminants and the resultant clusters was generated. Finally, membership
 211 probabilities of isolates associated to a specific MLG and to a resultant cluster were calculated.

212 **3. Results**

213 **3.1 Sequencing analysis of aecial clusters**

214 A total of 124 aecial samples from 11 EU countries were successfully sequenced, which had high
 215 identity values (from 98.0% to 99.4%) to *P. graminis* reference samples from NCBI and collected
 216 from three different hosts, i.e., *T. aestivum*, *Dactylis glomerata* and *Lolium rigidum*
 217 (Supplementary Table 3). Subsequent phylogenetic analysis using a subset of 62 aecial samples
 218 representing all countries and hosts in addition to 19 *Puccinia* reference isolates collected from
 219 multiple cereal and grass hosts resulted in two distinct clades (Fig. 2, Supplementary Table 2 and

220 3). One clade consisted of 30 aecial samples from seven countries with identity values
221 corresponding to *P. graminis* samples collected from *D. glomerata* and *L. rigidum*, which grouped
222 with *P. graminis* reference samples from *A. sativa* and other grasses, including *D. glomerata*, *L.*
223 *rigidum*, *L. perenne*, *Festuca elatior* and *Agrostis stolonifera*. Some level of subgrouping was
224 observed within clade 1, where aecial samples grouped primarily with *P. graminis* reference
225 samples from different grass species. To note, some aecial samples did not clearly group with any
226 of the reference samples as in the case of those from Italy, France and most of the samples from
227 Spain and Latvia. A second clade comprised 32 aecial samples from nine countries with identity
228 values corresponding to *P. graminis* samples collected from *T. aestivum*. These samples grouped
229 with *P. graminis* reference samples from *T. aestivum*, *S. cereale* and *Elymus caninus*. No clear
230 subgrouping was observed within clades 2, the sequence analysis was unable to distinguish
231 between closely related ff. spp. of *P. graminis* infecting wheat and rye. The *P. striiformis* reference
232 isolate infecting wheat and related *Puccinia* species infecting multiple grasses clearly formed an
233 outgroup (Fig. 2).

Cereal stem rust undergo sexual reproduction in Europe

234

235 **Figure 2.** Phylogenetic analysis of the translation elongation factor 1- α (EF1- α) gene amplified for 62 aecial
 236 samples collected in 11 European countries and 19 *Puccinia graminis* reference isolates collected from
 237 multiple hosts (accession numbers from NCBI-add missing ones). Sequences from *P. striiformis* and related
 238 species were included as outliers. Bootstrap values for 1000 replicates are shown when >75%. Scale bar
 239 indicates nucleotide substitutions per site.

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Cereal stem rust undergo sexual reproduction in Europe

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243 3.2 Aecial host specificity studies

244 Aecial samples from three EU countries (Spain, UK, and Switzerland) successfully produced stem
 245 rust infections on varieties of wheat, barley, rye and oat indicating the presence of multiple special
 246 forms of stem rust within the aecial samples investigated, e.g., *Pgt*, *Pgs* and *Pga* (Table 1). A total
 247 of 533 single lesions of stem rust were recovered, which varied across countries and cereal
 248 varieties. *Puccinia striiformis* infecting cereals was not detected on any of the aecial samples
 249 analyzed.

250 **Table 1.** Number of single lesions of *Puccinia graminis* derived from barberry leaves bearing aecia sampled
 251 in three European countries and recovered on multiple varieties of four major cereal crops (na: not assessed).

Population	Cereal crops			
	Wheat	Barley	Rye	Oat

Cereal stem rust undergo sexual reproduction in Europe

	Line E	Morocco	Cartago	Hiproly	Palazzo	Marvelous	Total
Spain	206	42	na	89	24	51	412
UK	19	4	na	29	7	0	59
Switzerland	1	na	19	na	42	na	62

252

253 3.3 Genetic diversity and variance of sexual populations

254 Prior analysis, the suitability of the SSR markers was assessed by generating a genotype
 255 accumulation curve that plots the number of multilocus genotypes (MLGs) against the number of
 256 loci (Supplementary Figure 1), which showed that the 19 loci applied in the present study were
 257 sufficient to discriminate between individuals in the dataset. Population genetic analyses was
 258 performed on a subset of 192 single stem rust isolates collected from wheat, rye and barley. The
 259 19 SSR markers identified 135 multilocus genotypes (MLGs) (Table 2, Supplementary Table 3).
 260 The allelic genotypes of each of the 192 isolates and their host of origin and corresponding MLG
 261 at the 19 SSR loci are provided in Supplementary Table 4. The highest number of MLGs was
 262 detected in the Spanish population followed by UK and Switzerland. Individual MLGs were not
 263 resampled among the three populations. Conversely, four MLGs (21, 27, 33 and 35) detected in
 264 the Spanish population were resampled from two hosts, i.e. wheat and barley. High genotypic
 265 richness (0.53-0.93), genotypic diversity (0.93-0.99), evenness of genotype abundance (0.63-0.97)
 266 and gene diversity (0.64-0.81) were observed among the three sexual populations (Table 2).

267 **Table 2.** Genetic diversity parameters of sexually derived *Puccinia graminis* isolates from three European
 268 populations at 19 microsatellite loci.

Population	N ^b	MLGs ^c	Genotypic richness ^d	Genotypic diversity ^e	Evenness index ^f	Gene diversity ^g
Spain	124	93	0.75	0.99	0.78	0.64
UK	53	28	0.53	0.96	0.63	0.73
Switzerland	15	14	0.93	0.93	0.97	0.81
Total ^a	192	135	0.70	0.99	0.69	0.74

269 ^a Indices calculated for pooled populations.

270 ^b Number of genotyped samples.

271 ^c Number of multilocus genotypes.

272 ^d Number of MLGs divided by number of genotyped samples.

273 ^e Simpson's genotypic diversity index.

274 ^f Evenness of genotype abundance index (E_s).

275 ^g Nei's unbiased gene diversity (H_{exp}).

276

277 3.4 Spatial differentiation and structure of sexual populations

278 The AMOVA results revealed significant variations by the two hierarchies analysed (population
 279 and host) (Table 4). The highest variation was observed within samples for the two hierarchies
 280 (67%-72%). Genetic differences among samples within populations and hosts accounted for 19%
 281 and 27%, respectively. The lowest variation was observed among hosts (1%). Variation among
 282 populations explained 14% of the total variance. Subsequent individual AMOVA pairwise

283 comparisons between populations revealed that the source of variation between Spain and UK
 284 increased up to 16%, decreased to 13% for Spain and Switzerland and significantly decreased to
 285 2% for UK and Switzerland. The other two sources of variation (among samples within populations
 286 and within samples) resulted in similar values as those in Table 4 (Supplementary Table 5).

287 **Table 4.** Analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) of *Puccinia graminis* isolates for two individual
 288 hierarchies (population and host) based on clone-corrected data.

Source of variation	Df ^a	Sum of squares	Mean of squares	Estimated variance	Variation (%)	p-value ^b
Population						
Among populations	2	301.64	150.82	2.11	14	<0.001
Among samples within populations	132	2153.95	16.32	2.95	19	<0.001
Within samples	135	1406.04	10.42	10.42	67	<0.001
Host						
Among hosts	2	62.19	31.10	0.15	1	0.004
Among samples within hosts	136	2466.94	18.14	3.89	27	<0.001
Within samples	139	1439.32	10.36	10.36	72	<0.001

289 ^aDegrees of freedom, ^bp-values based on 1999 permutations.

290 Pairwise comparisons for genetic differentiation between populations based on F_{st} values, Nei's
 291 genetic distances and number of effective migrants (N_m) are shown in Table 3. Fixation indexes
 292 for the population from Spain vs. UK and Switzerland resulted on significant values ranging from
 293 0.084 to 0.125, from 0.446 to 0.708 for the Nei's genetic distance and from 1.747 and 2.742 for the
 294 N_m . This indicates a moderate to high genetic differentiation between the population from Spain
 295 compared to UK and Switzerland. In contrast, lower values of F_{st} and Nei's genetic distance and
 296 higher values of N_m were observed for UK vs. Switzerland, suggesting a low genetic
 297 differentiation between these two populations. The correlation coefficient between the F_{st} and the
 298 Nei's genetic distance values was close to one ($\rho=0.99$), implying a high correlation between these
 299 two genetic differentiation parameters. The number of effective migrants was inversely correlated
 300 to F_{st} ($\rho=-0.97$) and Nei's genetic distance values ($\rho=-0.97$).

301 **Table 3.** Pairwise genetic differentiation among populations measured by the fixation index based on
 302 Wright's F statistics (F_{st}), the number of effective migrants (N_m) and Nei's genetic distance. Clone-
 303 corrected data confirmed the results.

Population	F_{st}	Nei's genetic distance	N_m
Spain vs. UK	0.125*	0.708	1.747
Spain vs. Switzerland	0.084*	0.446	2.742
UK vs. Switzerland	0.051	0.220	4.696

304 *Significant at $p < 0.001$

305 To infer in the genetic structure among the three populations, a DAPC analysis was conducted
 306 using the 135 MLGs detected in this study. The DAPC analysis revealed four genetic clusters based
 307 on 20 PCs retained and three discriminant eigenvalues (Fig. 2). The optimal number of clusters
 308 corresponded with the lowest value of the elbow observed in the BIC curve, $K=4$ (Fig. 3). The 135
 309 MLGs detected were clustered based on membership probabilities larger than 0.999

310 (Supplementary Table 6). Cluster 1, 2 and 3 consisted of 15, 20 and 58 isolates from the Spanish
 311 population, respectively. Each of these clusters corresponded with isolates derived from aecial
 312 samples collected in local and distinct barberry areas (Supplementary Figure 3, Supplementary
 313 Table 5). Cluster 4 consisted of 42 isolates from both UK and Switzerland. Subsequent DAPC
 314 clustering at either K=5 or K=6 did not result in further subgrouping of CL4 (data not shown). No
 315 subgrouping was observed based on host of origin where samples originated from all three hosts
 316 (wheat, barley and rye) were represented on each of the four clusters (Fig. 4).

317 **Figure 3.** Discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) for the 135 multilocus genotypes (MLGs)
 318 detected among the 192 *Puccinia graminis* isolates included, where the Bayesian Information Criterion
 319 (BIC) supported four distinct genetic groups (bottom-left inset). The axes represent the first two linear
 320 discriminants. Each colored ellipsis represents distinct genetic clusters and symbols individual isolates
 321 associated with unique MLGs. Eigenvalues indicate the amount of genetic information retained by the PCA
 322 (bottom-right inset) and the discriminant function (DA, top-right inset).

324 **Figure 4.** Number of samples originated from wheat, barley and rye and represented on each of the four
 325 clusters identified in the DAPC analysis.
 326

327

328 **4. Discussion**

329 Over the last decade, increasing reports of stem rust across Europe have raised concerns about the
 330 potential role of *Berberis* spp. in the epidemiology of stem rust infecting major cereal crops
 331 (Saunders et al., 2019). As a result, a European global initiative was launched aiming to develop
 332 an early-warning system for cereal rusts where the role of the alternate host in rust epidemiology
 333 was considered as a crucial part (ref.). Here, we identified the *Puccinia* species that infect the
 334 alternate host, barberry species, across Europe, evaluated which stem rust species undergo sexual
 335 reproduction and infect major cereal crops and we finally investigated the genetic diversity and
 336 structure of sexually-derived populations infecting cereal hosts.

337 **Barberry species as source of rust inoculum**

338 *Berberis* (barberry) is a widely distributed genus with approximately 500 species described
 339 globally (Ahrendt, 1961). The current and widespread prevalence of barberry spp. across Europe,
 340 mainly due to the repeal of eradication laws and the reintroduction for environmental purposes,
 341 emphasize the need to monitor the potential spread of rust fungi to adjacent cereal crops (Berlin et
 342 al., 2013b;Saunders et al., 2019). By a systematic sampling approach across Europe, we were able
 343 to confirm the presence of multiple barberry species, with most harboring multiple aecial
 344 infections, in multiple locations and under different ecological conditions. For instance, infected
 345 barberry plants were found growing in close proximity to cereal and grass crops at multiple
 346 locations across Europe, which may have a strong influence in the epidemiology of cereal rust
 347 fungi and pose a threat to cereal production. The barberry species identified included the widely
 348 distributed common barberry and three indigenous barberry species present in Spain and Italy.
 349 Additionally, aecial infections were sampled from *B. x ottawensis*, an interspecific hybrid of the
 350 susceptible common barberry and the resistant Japanese barberry, *B. thunbergii*. This highlights
 351 the importance of monitoring naturally occurring interspecific hybrids, which have previously been
 352 overlooked and may play a crucial role in the epidemiology of cereal rust fungi (Bartaula et al.,
 353 2018). Additionally, the presence of resistant barberry species such as *B. thunbergii* either
 354 naturalized or as ornamentals, emphasize the need to reconsider the potential risk these may have
 355 in creating novel susceptible hybrids which may have a profound effect in the epidemiology of
 356 cereal rust fungi.

357 **Identification of *Puccinia* species infecting barberry**

358 In the present study, the EF1- α gene was selected due to its suitability to study closely related
 359 species within the *Puccinia* genus due to the presence of highly variable introns (van der Merwe et
 360 al., 2008). Sequencing analysis confirmed the presence of two main clades including multiple
 361 special forms of *P. graminis* infecting *Berberis* spp. across Europe. One clade comprised *P.*
 362 *graminis* ff. spp. *tritici* and *secalis* infecting wheat and rye, respectively, in addition to bearded
 363 wild rye, *Elymus caninus*. A second clade included *P. graminis* f.sp. *avenae* infecting oat and
 364 multiple grasses such as ryegrass (*L. perenne*) and orchard grass (*D. glomerata*). This is in line
 365 with previous studies using the EF1- α and the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region where ff.
 366 spp. infecting wheat and rye were closely related whereas those infecting oat, ryegrass and orchard
 367 grass clearly formed a separated group (Zambino and Szabo, 1993;Berlin et al., 2013a;Lewis et al.,
 368 2018). Some level of subgrouping was observed within clade II, which probably indicates the
 369 presence of additional special forms and/or subspecies infecting related wild grasses as stem rust

370 can infect more than 300 grass species belonging to multiple genera (Anikster, 1984). Although
371 multiple ff. spp. of *P. graminis* may coexist within the same area, hybridization between these
372 appeared to be rather limited and restricted to occur at some degree between ff. spp. genetically
373 related. For example, sexual crosses between *Pgt* and *Pgs* resulted in the generation of viable
374 progeny under controlled conditions. In contrast, crosses between *Pgt* and *Pga* rarely occur and
375 lack the generation of aecial structures probably due to the involvement of reproductive barriers
376 between non-genetically related ff. spp. (Johnson, 1949).

377 Additionally, *in vivo* experiments using aecial samples resulted in successful stem rust infection in
378 susceptible cultivars of major cereal crops (wheat, barley, rye and oat) indicating the presence of
379 multiple ff. spp. of *P. graminis*. Similar results have been reported when using aecial infections
380 collected from a local sexual population in Spain (Villegas et al., 2022). Stem rust lesions were
381 observed on wheat and rye, which probably indicate the presence of ff. spp. *tritici* and *secalis*,
382 respectively. The same may be applied to the stem rust lesions obtained from barley, which could
383 be a result of either of these two ff. spp. (Anikster, 1984). Although it cannot be ruled out that host
384 overlapping between special forms of *P. graminis* may occur as a result of sexual hybridization
385 between ff. spp. (Green, 1971). A number of stem rust lesions were obtained from oat, which
386 probably indicates the presence of *Pga*. Although it could also be that the resulting stem rust
387 infections were a result of different special forms and/or subspecies infecting other grass hosts as
388 *P. graminis* is able to infect multiple grass species (Anikster, 1984). Accessory hosts such as wild
389 cereals and grasses may play a crucial role in the epidemiology of stem rust as these could be
390 function as an important source of inoculum to maintain stem rust infections in the absence of
391 cereal crops. Host specificity analysis by cross-infection studies using a collection of different
392 grasses and fungal strains, could help to obtain novel insights into host specialization and to
393 evaluate the potential risk of stem rust spreading between different cereal and grass hosts.

394 Equally important as stem rust, the yellow rust fungus infecting wheat undergo sexual reproduction
395 on members of the *Berberidacea* family (Jin et al., 2010;Mehmood et al., 2020). The sexual cycle
396 of *P. striiformis* has only been reported to occur in China at low frequencies, where barberry is
397 ubiquitous and frequently growing alongside wheat crops (Zhao et al., 2013;Wang et al., 2016).
398 The increased prevalence of barberry spp. across Europe and the reported susceptibility under
399 controlled conditions of multiple barberry spp. to *P. striiformis* strains widely present in Europe
400 stress the importance of continue searching in areas where conducive conditions for completion
401 of the sexual cycle may occur (Rodriguez-Algaba et al., 2017;2020;2021).

402 **Genetic diversity and spatial differentiation**

403 The application of neutral molecular markers have proven very useful to infer in the genetic
404 variability and structure among cereal rust populations (e.g., Berlin et al., 2012;Hovmøller et al.,
405 2016;Kolmer et al., 2019). Here, the application of SSR markers on progeny derived from three
406 sexual populations of *P. graminis* allowed to confirm that high genetic diversity is generated after
407 sexual reproduction on the alternate host. This was exemplified by high number of MLGs and
408 genetic diversity indexes. Sexual reproduction favors gene reshuffling leading to the generation of
409 novel gene combinations with the potential of causing detrimental effects for cereal crop
410 production (Roelfs and Groth, 1980;Jin, 2011). Indeed, high genetic variability and races carrying
411 unusual virulence combinations associated with the sexual cycle have been reported using *P.*
412 *graminis* samples collected from wheat, rye and oat (Berlin et al., 2013b;Berlin et al., 2014;Olivera

413 Firpo et al., 2017;Olivera et al., 2019). More recently, high genetic diversity with respect to
414 virulence and microsatellite markers were detected in samples collected from wheat, rye and
415 creeping wild rye (*Elymus repens*) in Spain and from wheat and barley in Sweden in areas where
416 the alternate host is locally present (ref.).

417 Analysis of molecular variance of the sexual populations from Spain, UK and Switzerland revealed
418 that the highest genetic variability was observed within and among samples, which is in line with
419 the high genetic diversity observed based on the number of MLGs and diversity parameters.
420 Genetic variation among populations explained 14% of the total variance, which significantly
421 decreased to 2% in a pairwise comparison between sexual populations from UK and Switzerland.
422 Pairwise comparisons for genetic differentiation between populations from UK and Switzerland
423 based on F_{st} values, Nei's genetic distance and N_m revealed a moderate to low genetic
424 differentiation and high gene flow between populations (Wright, 1965;Nei, 1972;Sharma-Poudyal
425 et al., 2020). In contrast, the comparison between Spain and the other two sexual populations
426 suggested a significantly higher genetic differentiation and lower genetic exchange between
427 populations. The DAPC, a multivariate analysis without any predetermination with respects to
428 Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium or linkage disequilibrium (Jombart et al., 2010), provided additional
429 clues about the genetic structure and differentiation of the sexual populations. Four distinct clusters
430 were identified, where three of them belonged to *P. graminis* samples derived from three locally
431 separated locations in Spain. This probably indicated that each of these populations were originated
432 as a result of infections on nearby barberry plants and that gene flow did not influence the formation
433 of these populations. A forth cluster was comprised of isolates derived from UK and Switzerland.
434 This is consistent with the low genetic differentiation observed between these two populations
435 based on results from AMOVA analysis, F_{st} values, Nei's genetic distance and N_m . Indeed, gene
436 flow due to aerial dispersal of fungal inocula over long distances is a common phenomenon
437 previously reported for rust fungi (Nagarajan and Singh, 1990;Brown and Hovmöller, 2002).
438 Additionally, a possible explanation of the low genetic differentiation observed between the
439 populations from UK and Switzerland could be that both sexual populations were originated by
440 common parental ancestors which underwent sexual reproduction on distant barberry areas. Lastly,
441 the DAPC analysis revealed no sub-clustering based on host of origin of the sexually-derived
442 isolates infecting wheat, rye and barley. As previously discussed, the lack of differentiation
443 between ff. spp. infecting wheat, rye and barley could be due to genetic similarities between these
444 ff. spp. and probably the existence of some level of overlapping in host range.

445 This study certainly demonstrated that the sexual cycle of stem rust infecting cereals and grasses
446 frequently occurs in multiple European countries which underlines the need to reinitiate rust
447 resistance breeding strategies to enhance cereal crop defenses in case stem rust becomes prevalent
448 in Europe. Future screen of cereal germplasm commonly grown in Europe using the sexual
449 populations generated in this study will allow to assess the current level of stem rust susceptibility
450 of the European cereal germplasm and asses which resistance genes are more likely to evolve
451 towards new virulences and hence put at risk the durability of specific resistance genes. This will
452 help to select resistance genes and combinations thereof, which are expected to be more durable,
453 and develop more sustainable disease management and resistance deployment strategies.

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456 **5. Conflict of Interest**

457 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
458 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

459 **6. Author Contributions**

460 JRA, MSH and AFJ conceived and designed the study. JRA wrote the manuscript with
461 contributions from AFJ and MSH. JRA performed the recovery of aecial samples on cereal hosts.
462 JRA and AJ facilitated sampling in barberry areas in Denmark. JRA and AFJ performed the SSR
463 genotyping and DNA sequencing data analyses. PS and KF recovered aecial samples from fungal
464 material collected in Switzerland and facilitated sampling in barberry areas in Germany. JAZ, JA
465 and FM, BR, PC, LF, SS, AH, SH and SW and FS and ML facilitated sampling strategies in Spain,
466 Switzerland, Italy, Latvia, Slovakia, Czech Republic, UK and France, respectively. JGH developed
467 the graphical representation of results. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

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475 **9. Data Availability Statement**

476 The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/supplementary material.
477 The EF1- α sequence data reported in this the present study were deposited in GenBank (NCBI)
478 under the accession numbers listed in Supplementary Table 2 and Supplementary Table 3.

479 **References**

- 480 Abbasi, M., Goodwin, S.B., and Scholler, M. (2005). Taxonomy, phylogeny, and distribution of
481 *Puccinia graminis*, the black stem rust: new insights based on rDNA sequence data.
482 *Mycoscience* 46, 241-247, doi:10.1007/s10267-005-0244-x
- 483 Ahrendt, L.W.A. (1961). *Berberis* and *Mahonia*. A taxonomic revision. *J. Linn. Soc. London Bot.*
484 369, 1–410, doi:10.1111/j.1095-8339.1961.tb00889.x
- 485 Altschul, S.F., Madden, T.L., Schäffer, A.A., Zhang, J., Zhang, Z., Miller, W., and Lipman, D.J.
486 (1997). Gapped BLAST and PSI-BLAST: a new generation of protein database search
487 programs. *Nucleic acids research* 25, 3389-3402, doi:10.1093/nar/25.17.3389
- 488 Anikster, Y. (1984). "The formae speciales," in *The Cereal Rusts*, eds. W.R. Bushness & A.P.
489 Roelfs. (Orlando, FL.: Academic Press), 124-137

- 490 Bartaula, R., Melo, A.T.O., Connolly, B.A., Jin, Y., and Hale, I. (2018). An interspecific barberry
 491 hybrid enables genetic dissection of non-host resistance to the stem rust pathogen
 492 *Puccinia graminis*. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 69, 2483-2493,
 493 doi:10.1093/jxb/ery066
- 494 Berlin, A. (2017). *Stem rust attacks in Sweden heralds the return of a previously vanquished foe*.
 495 *Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, SLU News*. [https://www.slu.se/en/ew-](https://www.slu.se/en/ew-news/2017/11/stem-rust-attacks-in-sweden-heralds-the-return-of-a-previously-vanquished-foe/)
 496 [news/2017/11/stem-rust-attacks-in-sweden-heralds-the-return-of-a-previously-](https://www.slu.se/en/ew-news/2017/11/stem-rust-attacks-in-sweden-heralds-the-return-of-a-previously-vanquished-foe/)
 497 [vanquished-foe/](https://www.slu.se/en/ew-news/2017/11/stem-rust-attacks-in-sweden-heralds-the-return-of-a-previously-vanquished-foe/) [Online]. [Accessed 19.02 2022].
- 498 Berlin, A., Djurle, A., Samils, B., and Yuen, J. (2012). Genetic variation in *Puccinia graminis*
 499 Collected from Oats, Rye, and Barberry. *Phytopathology* 102, 1006-1012., doi:
- 500 Berlin, A., Kyaschenko, J., Justesen, A.F., and Yuen, J. (2013a). Rust Fungi Forming Aecia on
 501 *Berberis* spp. in Sweden. *Plant Disease* 97, 1281-1287, doi:10.1094/pdis-10-12-0989-re
- 502 Berlin, A., Rahmatov, M., Muminjanov, H., and Yuen, J. (2014). Sexual reproduction contributes
 503 to genotypic variation in the population of *Puccinia graminis* in Tajikistan. *European*
 504 *Journal of Plant Pathology* 141, 159-168, doi:10.1007/s10658-014-0534-2
- 505 Berlin, A., Samils, B., and Andersson, B. (2017). Multiple genotypes within aecial clusters in
 506 *Puccinia graminis* and *Puccinia coronata* improved understanding of the biology of
 507 cereal rust fungi. *Fungal. Biol. Biotechnol.* 4:3, doi:10.1186/s40694-017-0032-3
- 508 Berlin, A., Samils, B., Djurle, A., Wirsén, H., Szabo, L., and Yuen, J. (2013b). Disease
 509 development and genotypic diversity of *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *avenae* in Swedish oat
 510 fields. *Plant Pathology* 62, 32-40, doi:10.1111/j.1365-3059.2012.02609.x
- 511 Bhattacharya, S. (2017). Deadly new wheat disease threatens Europe's crops. *Nature* 542, 145-
 512 146, doi:10.1038/nature.2017.21424
- 513 Billiard, S., Lopez-Villavicencio, M., Hood, M.E., and Giraud, T. (2012). Sex, outcrossing and
 514 mating types: unsolved questions in fungi and beyond. *J. Evolution. Biol.* 25, 1002–1231,
 515 doi:10.1111/j.1420-9101.2012.02495.x
- 516 Brown, J.K., and Hovmøller, M.S. (2002). Aerial dispersal of pathogens on the global and
 517 continental scales and its impact on plant disease. *Science* 297, 537-541,
 518 doi:10.1126/science.1072678
- 519 Burdon, J.J., and Roelfs, A.P. (1985). The effect of sexual and asexual reproduction on the
 520 isozyme structure of populations of *Puccinia graminis*. *Phytopathology* 75, 1068–1073,
 521 doi:10.1094/Phyto-75-1068
- 522 Cummins, B., and Greene, H.C. (1966). A review of the grass rust fungi that have uredial
 523 paraphyses and aecia on *Berberis mahonia* *Mycologia* 58, 702-721, doi:10.2307/3756846
- 524 Eriksson, J., and Henning, E. (1894). Die Hauptresultate einer neuen Untersuchung über die
 525 Getreiderostpilze. *Z. Pflanzenkr* 4, 197-203, doi:
- 526 Excoffier, L., Smouse, P.E., and Quattro, J.M. (1992). Analysis of molecular variance inferred
 527 from metric distances among DNA haplotypes: application to human mitochondrial-DNA
 528 restriction data. *Genetics* 131, 479–491, doi:10.1093/genetics/131.2.479

- 529 Green, G.J. (1971). Hybridization between *Puccinia graminis tritici* and *Puccinia graminis secalis*
 530 and its evolutionary implications. *Canadian Journal of Botany* 49, 2089-2095,
 531 doi:10.1139/b71-294
- 532 Grünwald, N.J., Goodwin, S.B., Milgroom, M.G., and Fry, W.E. (2003). Analysis of genotypic
 533 diversity data for populations of microorganisms. *Phytopathology* 93, 738–746,
 534 doi:10.1094/PHYTO.2003.93.6.738
- 535 Hermansen, J.E. (1968). *Studies on the spread and survival of cereal rust and mildew diseases in*
 536 *Denmark*. Doctor of Science thesis, The Royal Veterinary and Agricultural University.
- 537 Hovmøller, M.S. (2018). *Rustwatch Wheat Rust Early Warning*.
 538 <http://agro.au.dk/forskning/projekter/rustwatch/> [Online]. [Accessed].
- 539 Hovmøller, M.S., Rodriguez-Algaba, J., Thach, T., and Sørensen, C.K. (2017). "Race Typing of
 540 *Puccinia striiformis* on Wheat," in *Wheat Rust Diseases, Methods and Protocols*, ed. S.
 541 Periyannan. (N.Y., U.S.A.: Springer Protocols, Methods in Molecular Biology), 29-40.
- 542 Hovmøller, M.S., Walter, S., Bayles, R.A., Hubbard, A., Flath, K., Sommerfeldt, N., Leconte,
 543 M., Czembor, P., Rodriguez-Algaba, J., Thach, T., Hansen, J.G., Lassen, P., Justesen,
 544 A.F., Ali, S., and De Vallavieille-Pope, C. (2016). Replacement of the European wheat
 545 yellow rust population by new races from the centre of diversity in the near-Himalayan
 546 region. *Plant Pathol.* 65, 402-411, doi:
- 547 Jin, Y. (2011). Role of *Berberis* spp. as alternate hosts in generating new races of *Puccinia*
 548 *graminis* and *P. striiformis*. *Euphytica* 179, 105-108, doi:10.1007/s10681-010-0328-3
- 549 Jin, Y., Szabo, L.J., and Carson, M. (2010). Century-old mystery of *Puccinia striiformis* life
 550 history solved with the identification of *Berberis* as an alternate host. *Phytopathology*
 551 100, 432-435, doi:10.1094/PHYTO-100-5-0432
- 552 Johnson, T. (1949). INTERVARIETAL CROSSES IN PUCCINIA GRAMINIS. *Canadian*
 553 *Journal of Research* 27c, 45-65, doi:10.1139/cjr49c-004
- 554 Jombart, T. (2008). adegenet: a R package for the multivariate analysis of genetic markers.
 555 *Bioinformatics* 24, 1403-1405, doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btn129
- 556 Jombart, T., Devillard, S., and Balloux, F. (2010). Discriminant analysis of principal
 557 components: a new method for the analysis of genetically structured populations. *BMC*
 558 *Genetics* 11, 94, doi:10.1186/1471-2156-11-94
- 559 Kamvar, Z.N., Brooks, J.C., and Grünwald, N.J. (2015). Novel R tools for analysis of genome-
 560 wide population genetic data with emphasis on clonality *Front. Genet.* 6, 208,
 561 doi:10.3389/fgene.2015.00208
- 562 Kamvar, Z.N., Tabima, J.F., and Grünwald, N.J. (2014). Poppr: an R package for genetic analysis
 563 of populations with clonal, partially clonal, and/or sexual reproduction. *PeerJ* 2, e281,
 564 doi:10.7717/peerj.281
- 565 Kolmer, J.A., Ordoñez, M.E., German, S., Morgounov, A., Pretorius, Z., Visser, B., Goyeau, H.,
 566 Anikster, Y., and Acevedo, M. (2019). Multilocus Genotypes of the Wheat Leaf Rust
 567 Fungus *Puccinia triticina* in Worldwide Regions Indicate Past and Current Long-Distance
 568 Migration. *Phytopathology*® 109, 1453-1463, doi:10.1094/phyto-10-18-0411-r

- 569 Letunic, I., and Bork, P. (2021). Interactive Tree Of Life (iTOL) v5: an online tool for
570 phylogenetic tree display and annotation. *Nucleic Acids Research* 49, W293-W296,
571 doi:10.1093/nar/gkab301
- 572 Lewis, C.M., Persoons, A., Beber, D.P., Kigathi, R.N., Maintz, J., Findlay, K., Bueno-Sancho,
573 V., Corredor-Moreno, P., Harrington, S.A., Kangara, N., Berlin, A., García, R., Germán,
574 S.E., Hanzalová, A., Hodson, D.P., Hovmøller, M.S., Huerta-Espino, J., Imtiaz, M.,
575 Mirza, J.I., Justesen, A.F., Niks, R.E., Omrani, A., Patpour, M., Pretorius, Z.A.,
576 Roohparvar, R., Sela, H., Singh, R.P., Steffenson, B., Visser, B., Fenwick, P.M., Thomas,
577 J., Wulff, B.B.H., and Saunders, D.G.O. (2018). Potential for re-emergence of wheat stem
578 rust in the United Kingdom. *Communications Biology* 1, 13, doi:10.1038/s42003-018-
579 0013-y
- 580 López González, G. (1986). "Berberidaceae," in *Flora Iberica*, ed. G. López González. (Madrid,
581 Spain: Real Jardín Botánico, CSIC), 402-405.
- 582 Mehmood, S., Sajid, M., Zhao, J., Huang, L., and Kang, Z. (2020). Alternate hosts of *Puccinia*
583 *striiformis* f.sp. *tritici* and their role. *Pathogens* 9,434, doi:10.3390/pathogens9060434
- 584 Milus, E.A., Moon, D.E., Lee, K.D., and Mason, R.E. (2015). Race-Specific Adult-Plant
585 Resistance in Winter Wheat to Stripe Rust and Characterization of Pathogen Virulence
586 Patterns. *Phytopathology* 105, 1114-1122, doi:10.1094/PHYTO-11-14-0305-R
- 587 Naef, A., Roy, B.A., Kaiser, R., and Honegger, R. (2002). Insect-mediated reproduction of
588 systemic infections by *Puccinia arrhenatheri* on *Berberis vulgaris*. *New Phytol.* 154,
589 717–730, doi:10.1046/j.1469-8137.2002.00406.x
- 590 Nagarajan, S., and Singh, D.V. (1990). Long-Distance Dispersion of Rust Pathogens. *Annual*
591 *Review of Phytopathology* 28, 139-153, doi:10.1146/annurev.py.28.090190.001035
- 592 Nei, M. (1972). Genetic Distance between Populations. *The American Naturalist* 106, 283-292,
593 doi:
- 594 Nei, M. (1978). Estimation of average heterozygosity and genetic distance from a small number
595 of individuals. *Genetics* 89, 583–590, doi:10.1093/genetics/89.3
- 596 Olivera Firpo, P.D., Newcomb, M., Flath, K., Sommerfeldt-Impe, N., Szabo, L.J., Carter, M.,
597 Luster, D.G., and Jin, Y. (2017). Characterization of *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici*
598 isolates derived from an unusual wheat stem rust outbreak in Germany in 2013. *Plant*
599 *Pathology* 66, 1258-1266, doi:10.1111/ppa.12674
- 600 Olivera, P.D., Sikharulidze, Z., Dumbadze, R., Szabo, L.J., Newcomb, M., Natsarishvili, K.,
601 Rouse, M.N., Luster, D.G., and Jin, Y. (2019). Presence of a Sexual Population of
602 *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici* in Georgia Provides a Hotspot for Genotypic and
603 Phenotypic Diversity. *Phytopathology* 109, 2152-2160, doi:10.1094/PHYTO-06-19-0186-
604 R
- 605 Peakall, R., and Smouse, P.E. (2012). GenA1Ex 6.5: genetic analysis in Excel. Population genetic
606 software for teaching and research-an update. *Bioinformatics* 28, 2537-2539,
607 doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/bts460

- 608 Peakall, R.O.D., and Smouse, P.E. (2006). genalex 6: genetic analysis in Excel. Population
609 genetic software for teaching and research. *Molecular Ecology Notes* 6, 288-295,
610 doi:10.1111/j.1471-8286.2005.01155.x
- 611 Peterson, P.D. (2018). The Barberry Eradication Program in Minnesota for Stem Rust Control: A
612 Case Study. *Annual Review of Phytopathology* 56, 203-223, doi:10.1146/annurev-phyto-
613 080417-050133
- 614 Peterson, P.D., Leonard, K.J., Roelfs, A.P., and Sutton, T.B. (2005). Effect of barberry
615 eradication on changes in populations of *Puccinia graminis* in Minnesota. *Plant Dis.* 89,
616 935–940, doi:10.1094/PD-89-0935
- 617 Pretorius, Z.A., Singh, R.P., Wagoire, W.W., and Payne, T.S. (2000). Detection of Virulence to
618 Wheat Stem Rust Resistance Gene Sr31 in *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. tritici in Uganda. *Plant*
619 *Disease* 84, 203, doi:10.1094/PDIS.2000.84.2.203B
- 620 Rodriguez-Algaba, J., Hovmøller, M.S., and Justesen, A.F. (2020). Sexual recombination within
621 the “Kranich” race of the yellow rust fungus *Puccinia striiformis* f.sp. tritici on *Berberis*
622 *vulgaris*. *Europ. J. Plant Pathol.* 156, 1169–1173, doi:10.1007/s10658-019-01919-4
- 623 Rodriguez-Algaba, J., Hovmøller, M.S., Villegas, D., Cantero-Martínez, C., Jin, Y., and Justesen,
624 A.F. (2021). Two indigenous *Berberis* species from Spain were confirmed as alternate
625 hosts of the yellow rust fungus *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. tritici. *Plant Disease* 105, 2281-
626 2285, doi:10.1094/PDIS-02-21-0269-SC
- 627 Rodriguez-Algaba, J., Sørensen, C.K., Labouriau, R., Justesen, A.F., and Hovmøller, M.S.
628 (2017). Genetic diversity within and among aecia of the wheat rust fungus *Puccinia*
629 *striiformis* on the alternate host *Berberis vulgaris*. *Fungal Biol.* 12, 541-549,
630 doi:10.1016/j.funbio.2017.03.003
- 631 Roelfs, A.P. (1982). Effects of barberry eradication on stem rust in the United States. *Plant Dis.*
632 66, 177–181, doi:10.1094/PD-66-177
- 633 Roelfs, A.P. (1985). "Wheat and rye stem rust " in *The Cereal Rusts Vol. II: Diseases,*
634 *Distribution, Epidemiology, and Control* (Orlando, FL: A.P. Roelfs & W.R. Bushnell,
635 Academic Press), pp. 3–37.
- 636 Roelfs, A.P., and Groth, V.J. (1980). A comparison of virulence phenotypes in wheat stem rust
637 populations reproducing sexually and asexually. *Phytopathology* 70, 855–862, doi:
- 638 Saunders, D.G.O., Pretorius, Z.A., and Hovmøller, M.S. (2019). Tackling the re-emergence of
639 wheat stem rust in Western Europe. *Communications Biology* 2, 51, doi:10.1038/s42003-
640 019-0294-9
- 641 Sharma-Poudyal, D., Bai, Q., Wan, A., Wang, M., See, D., and Chen, X. (2020). Molecular
642 Characterization of International Collections of the Wheat Stripe Rust Pathogen *Puccinia*
643 *striiformis* f. sp. tritici Reveals High Diversity and Intercontinental Migration.
644 *Phytopathology* 110, 933-942, doi:10.1094/phyto-09-19-0355-r
- 645 Simpson, E.H. (1949). Measurement of diversity. *Nature* 163-688, doi:10.1038/163688a0
- 646 Singh, R.P., Hodson, D.P., Huerta-Espino, J., Jin, Y., Bhavani, S., Njau, P., Herrera-Foessel, S.,
647 Singh, P.K., Singh, S., and Govindan, V. (2011). The emergence of Ug99 races of the

- 648 stem rust fungus is a threat to world wheat production. *Annu Rev Phytopathol* 49, 465-
649 481, doi:10.1146/annurev-phyto-072910-095423
- 650 Singh, R.P., Singh, P.K., Rutkoski, J., Hodson, D.P., He, X., Jorgensen, L.N., Hovmoller, M.S.,
651 and Huerta-Espino, J. (2016). Disease Impact on Wheat Yield Potential and Prospects of
652 Genetic Control. *Annu Rev Phytopathol* 54, 303-322, doi:10.1146/annurev-phyto-080615-
653 095835
- 654 Stakman, E.C. (1923). Barberry eradication prevents black rust in Western Europe. *United States*
655 *Department of Agriculture*, 1–15, doi:
- 656 Stubbs, R.W. (1985). "Stripe rust," in *The Cereal Rusts Vol. II: Diseases, Distribution,*
657 *Epidemiology, and Control* (Orlando, FL: A.P. Roelfs and W.R. Bushnell, Academic
658 Press), 61-101.
- 659 Van Der Merwe, M.M., Walker, J., Ericson, L., and Burdon, J.J. (2008). Coevolution with higher
660 taxonomic host groups within the Puccinia/Uromyces rust lineage obscured by host
661 jumps. *Mycol Res* 112, 1387-1408, doi:10.1016/j.mycres.2008.06.027
- 662 Villegas, D., Bartaula, B., Cantero-Martínez, C., Luster, D., Szabo, L., Olivera, P., Berlin, A.,
663 Rodríguez-Algaba, J., Hovmøller, M., McIntosh, R., and Jin, Y. (2022). Barberry plays an
664 active role as an alternate host of Puccinia graminis in Spain. *Plant Pathology*,
665 doi:10.1111/ppa.13540
- 666 Wang, Z., Zhao, J., Chen, X., Peng, Y., Ji, J., Zhao, S., Lv, Y., Huang, L., and Kang, Z. (2016).
667 Virulence Variations of Puccinia striiformis f. sp. tritici Isolates Collected from Berberis
668 spp. in China. *Plant Disease* 100, 131-138, doi:10.1094/pdis-12-14-1296-re
- 669 Wright, S. (1965). The Interpretation of Population Structure by F-Statistics with Special Regard
670 to Systems of Mating. *Evolution* 19, 395-420, doi:10.2307/2406450
- 671 Yang, Z. (1994). Estimating the pattern of nucleotide substitution. *Journal of Molecular*
672 *Evolution* 39, 105-111, doi:10.1007/BF00178256
- 673 Zambino, P.J., Kubelik, A.R., and Szabo, L.J. (2000). Gene Action and Linkage of Avirulence
674 Genes to DNA Markers in the Rust Fungus Puccinia graminis. *Phytopathology* 90, 819-
675 826, doi:10.1094/PHYTO.2000.90.8.819
- 676 Zambino, P.J., and Szabo, L.J. (1993). Phylogenetic relationships of selected cereal and grass
677 rusts based on rDNA sequence analysis *Mycologia* 85, 401-414,
678 doi:10.1080/00275514.1993.12026292
- 679 Zhao, J., Wang, L., Wang, Z., Chen, X., Zhang, H., Yao, J., Zhan, G., Chen, W., Huang, L., and
680 Kang, Z. (2013). Identification of eighteen Berberis species as alternate hosts of Puccinia
681 striiformis f. sp. tritici and virulence variation in the pathogen isolates from natural
682 infection of barberry plants in China. *Phytopathology* 103, 927-934,
683 doi:10.1094/PHYTO-09-12-0249-R
- 684 Zhao, J., Wang, M., Chen, X., and Kang, Z. (2016). Role of alternate hosts in epidemiology and
685 pathogen variation of cereal rusts. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 54, 207-228,
686 doi:10.1146/annurev-phyto-080615-095851

687